

FIRMBACKBONE Privacy Statement

Version May 2026

If you use [FIRMBACKBONE](#) or if your company is included in our datasets, we may, under certain circumstances, need to collect and process your personal data. Below, we explain what personal data this involves, why we do so, what happens to your data, what your rights are, and who “we” are.

What is FIRMBACKBONE about?

FIRMBACKBONE is an organically growing longitudinal data infrastructure containing information on all Dutch companies and other registered organisations for the purposes of scientific research and education.

FIRMBACKBONE is an initiative of Utrecht University (lead partner) and VU University Amsterdam and obtain structural funding from the Dutch Ministry of Education, Culture and Science, via the [SSH Council](#) (Social Sciences and Humanities Council) in The Netherlands.

For what purpose do we process personal data?

Broadly speaking, we process personal data for two different purposes: to ‘populate’ our datasets and to grant access to those datasets.

Purpose 1: Data processing to ‘populate’ the datasets and facilitate scientific research

FIRMBACKBONE receives information about companies and other registered organisations from various data providers. The purpose of this data is to provide the academic community with information about the landscape of registered organisations that have been active in the Netherlands in recent years and have since ceased trading. It is expressly not the intention of this data to disclose information about individuals.

What categories of personal data might be included in the datasets, and why?

Personal data are defined as: any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person. In other words: information about a living person whose identity is known or can be ascertained. We process the following ‘regular’ personal data:

- Company name, which may correspond to an individual’s name
- Company address details, which may correspond to a private address
- Names of directors may appear in financial statements
- Personal names, telephone numbers, email addresses and address details found on company websites

How do we obtain these personal data?

Data is routinely supplied by the [Chamber of Commerce](#) (semi-annually) and by [LISA](#) (annually). Occasional data supplies may also come from other sources. In addition, we retrieve data from websites that have been flagged by [SIDN](#) as business websites (semi-annually).

Personal data may be obtained through:

- Text extracted from websites (only plain text is stored; we do not store images, video or audio). The application we use recognises and filters personal names, telephone numbers and email addresses. However, it is possible that not all of this data is filtered 100% correctly.
- Financial statements are supplied with much of the personal data redacted. However, it is possible that not all of this data is filtered 100% correctly.
- Data deliveries from data providers that accidentally contain more information than agreed.

What do we do to delete or anonymise personal data?

Our aim is not to share these personal data in any way. We do everything we reasonably can to ensure that the curated datasets made available to researchers do not contain personal data as defined in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

To ensure that no personal data are disclosed, several measures have been taken:

- Incoming data contains as little information about individuals as possible from the outset. The incoming data are only available to the FIRMBACKBONE data manager. In the exceptional case that name and address details are included, these are immediately removed by the data manager.
- The datasets are de-identified and certain data are obscured. The de-identification of company names is intended to ensure, for example, that no surnames remain. Furthermore, house numbers and street names are not disclosed, and postcodes and dates are obscured.
- The datasets are only available in a 'Trusted Secure Environment' for non-commercial research purposes. Only [SANE](#), a secure environment accepted by FIRMBACKBONE that applies the '[five safes principles](#)' endorsed by Statistics Netherlands (CBS), may be used to access the datasets. The data cannot be downloaded, and the export of results is only permitted following verification by FIRMBACKBONE. The export must not contain any information that can be traced back to a legal entity – and therefore not to an individual either.

How long do we retain personal data?

Personal data contained in the raw data (the incoming data) will be stored within Utrecht University's environment for as long as the infrastructure remains active. These data are accessible only to FIRMBACKBONE's data manager.

Are we allowed to process these personal data?

One of the statutory duties imposed on Utrecht University is the conduct of scientific research. This is a task in the public interest. Facilitating research by the university's own researchers and by other researchers falls within the scope of this duty. Fulfilling a task in the public interest is one of the legal grounds mentioned in the GDPR for processing personal data (Article 6(1)(e)). Should we process your personal data on this basis, you may [object to this](#), depending on your specific situation.

Purpose 2: Data processing for information about (potential) research projects

In order to get access to FIRMBACKBONE data, users will need to contact us. In doing so, we will store certain personal data. There are various scenarios (information requests, formal applications, use of datasets) in which the information requested and the duration of storage vary.

What categories of personal data do we collect, and why?

Personal data refer to any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person. In other words: information about a living person whose identity is known or can be ascertained.

Process	Regular personal data we process	Intended retention period
Request for information: contact, including via email, regarding access to the datasets and the opportunities they offer	Name, email address.	Short (we carry out a data purge every six months)
Formal application: following the assessment procedure	Name, student/researcher, affiliation, email address, description of research objective. For students, we ask for the course to which the application relates.	Average (1–2 years)
Use of datasets: Following approval and access	Name, student/researcher, affiliation, email address, which datasets, which research results have been released.	Long-term (no end date*) <i>* Required to link publications; for the sake of reproducibility, it must be recorded which datasets have been used in which environments</i>

How do we obtain these personal data?

It is the user themselves who provides the personal data described .

Do we share these personal data with others?

Personal data will not be shared with other individuals or organisations. The exception to this are data relating to which datasets are used and published results if research is being replicated. In such cases, FIRMBACKBONE will first attempt to contact the user.

Are we allowed to process this personal data?

We require these data to prepare a user agreement (i.e. to answer questions) and to enter into a user agreement with the user, regardless of whether or not a fee is payable for this agreement. Without these data, we cannot properly prepare and implement the user agreement.

How are your personal data protected?

Utrecht University has implemented a range of technical and organisational measures to ensure the best possible protection of your personal data against loss, data theft and unauthorised access. We report any instances of (attempted) misuse.

Is personal data used for automated decision-making or profiling?

No.

Is personal data exported to a country outside the European Economic Area?

Many countries outside the European Economic Area (EEA) offer a lower level of personal data protection than countries within the EEA. It is therefore important for you to know whether we intend to transfer personal data to a country outside the EEA. In relation to this project, we will not transfer personal data to a country outside the EEA.

What are your rights regarding our data processing activities?

Please note! You can only exercise the rights listed below if we are (still) able to identify which data relates to you.

Objecting

If we process your personal data on the grounds of [public interest](#), you have the right to object to the processing of your personal data. This means that, based on your specific circumstances, you may indicate that you do not wish us to process your personal data. You can do this by contacting the [contact person](#) for the project. Please state the reason(s) why you are objecting to the processing. We will then weigh your specific rights and interests against those of the project. If your rights and interests outweigh the interests of the project, we will cease processing your data and will delete your data.

Other rights: access, correction, erasure and complaints

You also have the right to know what personal data we hold about you and for what purpose we use it, and you have the right to have any inaccurate data corrected. In certain circumstances, you also have the right to have your data erased. Please contact the [project contact person](#).

Finally, you have the right to lodge a complaint. You can do so with the Data Protection Officer (DPO) at Utrecht University. You can contact the DPO by sending an email to: fg@uu.nl. If we are unable to resolve the matter, you can lodge a complaint with the Dutch data protection authority, the Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens. To do so, please visit www.autoriteitpersoonsgegevens.nl/en.

Do you still have questions?

If you have any further questions, please contact firbackbone@uu.nl.

Who is the data controller?

The data controller is the entity that determines the purposes and means of processing personal data. For this project, the data controller is:

Utrecht University
Heidelberglaan 8
3584 CS Utrecht

The Netherlands

Your contact person is: Rutger Schilpzand: firbackbone@uu.nl